

Research Article

Relationship between Social and Academic Adjustment: A Study of Female University Students in Azad Jammu and Kashmir

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 27-Mar-24 Revised: 29-Apr-24 Accepted: 04-May-24 Published: 05-May-24	The study was conducted to determine the relationship between social and academic adjustment of university-level female students AJ&K. The study was quantitative and descriptive in nature and survey method was employed together data from the respondents. The population of the study consisted of BS level students from University of Kotli AJ&K. The researcher selected 160 students as the sample using simple random sampling technique. The researcher personally visited university of Kotli and collected the data. In order to analyze the data, the researcher used frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. It was concluded that respondents feel nervous in front of teachers also they are good in academic work and they stated that academic work difficult in university. It is recommended that administration may encourage open communication between students and teachers to create a supportive environment.
Keywords:	Social Adjustment, Social Skills, Social Support, Self Confidence, Academic Adjustment, Prior Academic Preparation,
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Introduction

An individual's attempt to comply with the norms, morals, and regulations of a society to gain acceptance is social adjustment. It can be described as a mental procedure. It entails managing with fresh values and representatives. Accomplishment with the followers of culture as best one can is referred to as adjustment in psychology language (Alsaqqa, 2022).

The adjustment is commonly used in a variety of ways by psychologists to denote different social and relational contexts. Therefore, adjustment can be defined as the specific response to the masses and social constraints imposed upon them. Social adjustment is the effort of a person to conform to the norms, values and expectations of a community in order to gain taking. It is normally stated to as a mental framework. Production using new values and standards is involved. Receiving with the members of society as best as one can is referred to as adjustment in the logical language of psychology (Vansteenkiste, 2020).

Academic modifications are made to a student's approach to fulfilling the requirements of a course or academic program. Instead of lowering academic standards, these adjustments provide a gifted student with equitable access to the University's educational opportunities. Variations in a student's approach to the academic requirements of a course or program are known as academic adjustments. These modifications provide a qualified student with equitable access to the University's educational opportunities without falling academic standards. Academic changes might include, but are not limited to, substituting courses, extending deadlines, or using a different method to complete assignments (Syakur, 2020).

It is a legally required accommodation or service that provides an equal chance for a student with a handicap to gain from their education. Consider academic adjustment as a modification to the way things are typically done. In order to get satisfactory academic results, it states that students developed their coping skills and learning policies (Nurdin, 2022).

Experiences of discrimination have negative consequence on social adjustment, particularly in the later stages of adolescence. It has been demonstrated that adolescents who experience victimization tend to have lower levels of social competence, acceptance, and popularity. They also tend to be more alone and rejected, and their interactions with their peers are often worse. The degree to which an individual engages in suitable social behavior and adjusts to the existing social setting is known as social adjustment (Huang, 2020).

Academic Adjustment means a change or additional service associated to seminary prospectuses or to a database of study that enables a student with a capacity to receive an equal chance to help from educational processes and does not constitute a fundamental change. The process of adjusting involves overcoming obstacles, conflicts, and pressures while also attending to each person's needs. Students must decorate their performance in order to fit in at a new educational organization. They come from diverse backgrounds, each with their own standards and ideals. During the adjustment phase, the person tries to establish and maintain a harmonious relationship with its surroundings. In a university setting, almost all new students experience an adjustment period at their own rate of progress. Every student has a different degree of adjustment than the others, depending on their stage of development at that age (Udvari-Solner, & Thousand, 2018).

Students are required to submit appropriate paperwork demonstrating the importance of each suggested modification. If an academic adjustment will fundamentally alter a course, activity, job, or program requirement or create an unreasonable hardship, the College may refuse it. The connection with family, friends, and the school employees is social adjustment. School social adjustment is following the policies and guidelines of the educational institution. It is the capacity of a student to adjust to the rules and regulations while still being able to perform well in the classroom (Maynard, Garcia, Lucietto, Hutzel, & Newell, 2021).

A person's capacity to fulfill their basic needs, their knowledge and acceptance of who they are, their capacity to meet their desires, and their flexibility in responding to outside influences are all factors that contribute to their level of social adjustment. Teachers in high school have a significant impact on how well new pupils settle in (Yurizka, 2022).

Review of Related Literature

Social Adjustment

Social adjustment refers to an individual's ability to adapt and function effectively in various social situations. It involves navigating relationships, understanding societal norms, and finding a balance between personal needs and societal expectations. Successful social adjustment is crucial for overall well-being and can impact various aspects of life, including personal relationships, academic or professional success, and mental health. (Patel & Jansari, 2019).

At its core, social adjustment encompasses the development of social skills, emotional intelligence, and a sense of belonging within a community. These elements contribute to an individual's ability to establish and maintain meaningful connections with others. A well-adjusted person can communicate effectively, empathize with others, and handle conflicts in a constructive manner. (Raju & Rahimullah, 2007)

One key aspect of social adjustment is the ability to form and maintain interpersonal relationships. This begins in early childhood, as individuals learn to interact with family members, peers, and authority figures. Positive early experiences can lay the foundation for healthy relationship patterns, while negative experiences may result in challenges later in life (Wang & Sheikh-Khalil, 2014).

As individuals progress through adolescence and adulthood, they face increasingly complex social dynamics. Peer relationships become more significant, and the need for social acceptance can influence behavior and decision-making. The ability to navigate social hierarchies, understand social cues, and adapt to changing social norms becomes crucial during these stages. (Li & Zizzi, 2018).

Cultural and societal factors also play a significant role in social adjustment. Different cultures have distinct expectations regarding social behavior, communication styles, and interpersonal relationships. Individuals must learn to navigate these cultural nuances to function effectively in diverse social environments. Cultural competence, therefore, becomes an essential component of social adjustment (Hu, Liu, Zhang, & Wang, 2020).

Education plays a vital role in shaping social adjustment. School environments provide opportunities for social interaction and the development of interpersonal skills. Success in academic settings often requires collaboration, teamwork, and effective communication. Students who struggle with social adjustment may face challenges in forming study groups, participating in class discussions, or seeking help from teachers (Cawthra, 2020).

Workplaces present another arena where social adjustment is critical. Professional success often depends on one's ability to collaborate with colleagues, communicate ideas effectively, and navigate office dynamics. Networking and building positive relationships with supervisors and peers contribute significantly to career advancement and job satisfaction (Scanlan, Still, Radican, Henkel, Heffernan, Farrugia, P. & English, 2020).

Mental health is closely linked to social adjustment. Individuals who struggle with social interactions may experience feelings of isolation, loneliness, or rejection, which can contribute to mental health issues such as anxiety or depression. Conversely, positive social connections and a sense of belonging have been shown to enhance psychological well-being (Bedi, 2021).

Factors Affect Social Adjustment

Communication Skills

Effective communication is crucial for understanding and expressing oneself in social situations. Being able to listen attentively and empathetically to others is essential for understanding their perspectives, feelings, and needs. Active listening fosters better understanding and deeper connections in social interactions. Effective verbal communication involves clarity, coherence, and appropriateness in expressing thoughts, ideas, and emotions. Being able to articulate oneself clearly helps in conveying messages accurately and avoiding misunderstandings (Maloney, 2020).

Empathy

The ability to understand and share others' feelings fosters positive relationships. Empathy allows individuals to understand others' emotions, perspectives, and needs, which fosters trust, intimacy, and connection in relationships. People who demonstrate empathy are often better able to establish and maintain positive social connections, leading to improved social adjustment. Empathetic individuals are better equipped to navigate conflicts and disagreements because they can understand the emotions and motivations underlying others' behaviors. By empathizing with different perspectives, individuals can find mutually beneficial solutions and maintain harmony in social interactions (Decety, 2020)

Cultural Awareness

Awareness of and respect for cultural differences aids in navigating diverse social environments. Different cultures have distinct communication styles, including verbal and non-verbal cues. Being aware of these differences can help individuals navigate social interactions more effectively and avoid misunderstandings. Cultural norms and etiquette vary widely across different societies. Understanding and adhering to these norms can facilitate smoother social interactions and help individuals avoid inadvertently offending others (Sadiki, 2020).

Self-Confidence

Believing in oneself contributes to the ability to engage confidently in social interactions. On the other hand, individuals with low self-confidence may struggle in social settings. They may feel anxious or insecure, which can hinder their ability to interact effectively with others. This can lead to difficulties in forming relationships, participating in group activities, and asserting themselves in social situations. Overall, self-confidence plays a crucial role in social adjustment by influencing how individuals perceive themselves and interact with others. Building self-confidence through positive self-talk, setting achievable goals, and seeking support from others can help improve social adjustment and overall well-being (Feeney, 2022)

Flexibility

Being adaptable and open to new ideas helps in adjusting to different social contexts. Flexibility allows individuals to adapt to different social situations, environments, and expectations. This adaptability enables them to navigate various social interactions with ease and adjust their behavior accordingly. Flexible individuals are more open-minded and willing to consider different perspectives, ideas, and opinions. This openness fosters better communication and understanding in social settings, leading to smoother interactions and relationships (Babapour Chafi, 2021).

Conflict Resolution

The skill to resolve conflicts peacefully promotes harmonious social relationships. Conflict resolution promotes the development of healthier relationship dynamics by addressing underlying issues and finding mutually beneficial solutions. When conflicts are managed constructively, it strengthens relationships and fosters a supportive social network, contributing to positive social adjustment. Unresolved conflicts can create stress and tension within social interactions, leading to discomfort and strained relationships. By addressing and resolving conflicts promptly, individuals can alleviate this stress and tension, creating a more conducive environment for social adjustment (Naeem, 2020).

Social Skills

Basic social etiquette and interpersonal skills are essential for smooth social interactions. Conflict resolution promotes the development of healthier relationship dynamics by addressing underlying issues and finding mutually beneficial solutions. When conflicts are managed constructively, it strengthens relationships and fosters a supportive social network, contributing to positive social adjustment. Unresolved conflicts can create stress and tension within social interactions, leading to discomfort and strained relationships. By addressing and resolving conflicts promptly, individuals can alleviate this stress and tension, creating a more conducive environment for social adjustment (Valente, 2020).

Self-Concept

A positive self-image influences how one perceives and responds to social situations. Another aspect of self-concept that can impact social adjustment is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy refers to the belief in one's ability to accomplish tasks and achieve goals. People with high self-efficacy are

more likely to approach social interactions with confidence and persistence, leading to better social outcomes. Conversely, individuals with low self-efficacy may doubt their abilities to effectively navigate social situations, which can result in avoidance or withdrawal from social interactions (Schunk, 2021).

Resilience

The ability to bounce back from setbacks is crucial for maintaining social well-being. Resilience involves being flexible and adaptable in the face of change. This adaptability can help individuals navigate transitions in their social lives, such as moving to a new community, starting a new job, or experiencing changes in relationships. By being open to new experiences and opportunities, resilient individuals can more effectively adjust to their social environment. Resilience is often associated with a positive outlook and optimism about the future. This positive mindset can influence how individuals perceive and respond to social situations, leading to more constructive interactions and better social outcomes (Karman, 2020).

Social Support

Having a supportive network of friends and family aids in coping with challenges. Instrumental support involves tangible assistance such as financial help, practical assistance, or resources. For example, receiving help with job search or housing from friends or family can facilitate social adjustment by reducing barriers to success. Informational support involves providing advice, guidance, or information to help someone make informed decisions. Access to accurate information and helpful advice from supportive others can enhance an individual's ability to navigate social situations and adapt to new environments, leading to improved social adjustment (Cogan, Pret, & Cardon,, 2022).

Role of Social Adjustment of University Students

Social adjustment plays a crucial role in the overall well-being and success of university students. This multifaceted process involves adapting to new social environments, building relationships, and navigating the diverse challenges presented by university life. A successful social adjustment positively impacts academic performance, mental health, and future career prospects. Firstly, social adjustment facilitates the development of a supportive network. University environments are often characterized by diverse student populations, and establishing connections with peers can provide a sense of belonging and reduce feelings of isolation. Friendships and social bonds contribute to a student's emotional resilience, creating a safety net during times of stress or academic pressure (Credé, & Niehorster, 2012).

Moreover, social adjustment fosters the acquisition of crucial interpersonal skills. Students who engage in social activities, clubs, or group projects are more likely to enhance their communication, teamwork, and leadership abilities. These skills are not only valuable in a university setting but also translate into the professional world, preparing students for the demands of their future careers. Successful social adjustment positively influences mental health outcomes. University life can be overwhelming, with academic pressures, financial challenges, and personal growth all occurring simultaneously. Having a robust social support system aids in stress reduction and provides an outlet for emotional expression. Students who feel socially connected are less

prone to anxiety and depression, promoting a positive overall mental health experience (Назаров, 2021).

Furthermore, social adjustment contributes to a sense of identity formation. University is a time when individuals explore their interests, values, and beliefs. Interacting with diverse groups exposes students to different perspectives and worldviews, prompting self-reflection and personal growth. Through social interactions, students refine their identities, gaining a better understanding of who they are and what they aspire to become. In addition to personal development, social adjustment influences academic success. Collaborative learning and study groups, which are often formed through social interactions, enhance academic performance. The exchange of ideas, resources, and study strategies within a social context can improve comprehension and retention of academic material. Furthermore, students who feel socially connected are more likely to attend classes regularly and engage actively in academic pursuits. (Gray, Vitak, Easton, & Ellison, 2013).

However, challenges in social adjustment can hinder academic progress. Students who struggle to integrate socially may experience feelings of alienation or inadequacy, which can lead to academic disengagement. Addressing social adjustment issues early on is essential to prevent a negative impact on academic achievement. Cultural diversity on university campuses adds another layer to social adjustment. International students, in particular, face the challenge of adapting to a new cultural context. Universities must provide adequate support services, such as orientation programs and cultural sensitivity training, to facilitate the social adjustment of international students. Creating an inclusive environment that celebrates diversity enhances the overall university experience for both local and international students. In conclusion, the social adjustment of university students is a dynamic and influential process that extends beyond the immediate university experience. It shapes personal development, mental health, and academic success. Universities play a pivotal role in fostering a supportive and inclusive environment that facilitates positive social adjustment. By recognizing the importance of social integration, institutions can contribute to the holistic development of their students, preparing them not only for academic challenges but also for the complexities of a diverse and interconnected world (Gray, Vitak, Easton, & Ellison, 2013).

Academic Adjustment

It is a validly mandated adjustment or facility that provides an equal chance for a student with a incapacity to gain from their education. Consider academic adjustment as a change to the way things are typically done. Academic variations are tailored to each student's unique functional limits resulting from their disability. A DSPS faculty member, such as an academic counselor, learning disabilities professional, High-Tech Center instructor, or the ABI program leader, must discuss and authorize any necessary revisions (Simon, 2011).

The process through which students adjust to the intellectual demands, opportunities, and surroundings of educational settings is referred to as academic adjustment. It includes a range of elements of a student's academic experience, such as their performance in class, their study habits, their ability to manage their time well, and their capacity to thrive in a classroom. For children to excel academically and smoothly transition into educational institutions at various levels, such as elementary school, high school, college, or university, academic adjustment is crucial. (Rienties, Beausaert, Grohnert, Niemantsverdriet, & Kommers, 2012).

One key aspect of academic adjustment is adapting to the academic job and outlooks. Students must learn to manage their time effectively, set imports and develop study skills that align with the demands of their courses. This includes understanding assignment requirements, completing tasks within given deadlines, and keeping a balance between different subjects or courses. Academic adjustment also involves developing effective note-taking strategies, reading understanding skills and critical thinking abilities to involve with and understand the course material (Blake & Gallimore, 2021).

Furthermore, academic adjustment involves familiarizing to the instructional methods and learning styles employed in the educational institution. Students may encounter different teaching approaches such as lectures, group work or online learning, depending on the educational setting. Adjusting to these methods requires students to actively contribute in class discussions, engage with course materials and seek explanation when needed. Additionally, students may need to adapt to the grading system, evaluation methods and assessment formats utilized by their institution, which can impact their academic adjustment (Monroe, Plate, Oxarart, Bowers, & Chaves, 2019).

Academic adjustment also involves the social and emotional features of the academic situation. Students need to direct relationships with their teachers, classmates and other members of the educational community. This involves seeking support, asking questions and cooperating with peers. Additionally, managing the social and emotional pressures of academic performance, such as test nervousness or stress related to deadlines, is an important aspect of academic adjustment (Jones, & Bouffard, 2012).

Factors Affect Academic Adjustment

Several factors can impact academic adjustment, affecting students' ability to adapt to the academic demands and prospects of their educational settings (Domitrovich, Durlak, Staley, & Weissberg, 2017). Social-emotional competency: A crucial element in encouraging a good transition and lowering risk in school-age children.

Prior Academic Preparation

Students' prior academic preparation and educational experiences can provocation their ability to adjust academically. A strong foundation in fundamental skills and knowledge, such as reading, writing, and mathematics, can facilitate a smoother transition and adjustment to new academic environments (Garraway, 2021).

Learning Style and Preferences

Each student has unique learning styles and preferences. Some students may thrive in traditional classroom settings, while others may prefer more hands-on or experiential learning approaches. Misalignment between instructional methods and students' preferred learning styles can impede academic adjustment (Maynard, 2021).

Cultural and Linguistic Background

Students from diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds may face additional challenges in academic adjustment. Language barriers, unfamiliar academic practices and cultural differences

in classroom norms and expectations can impact their ability to fully engage and succeed educationally (Voevoda, 2020).

Personal Motivation and Mindset

Students' personal motivation and mindset can meaningfully impact their academic adjustment. A positive attitude, basic motivation, and a growth mindset contribute to resilience, perseverance, and a willingness to adapt to new academic challenges. Conversely, a lack of motivation or a fixed mindset can hinder adjustment and academic success (Hudig, 2023).

Student-Teacher Relationship

The quality of the student-teacher relationship can impact academic adjustment. Positive relationships characterized by trust, support, and effective communication stand in a conducive learning environment, where students feel comfortable seeking assistance and engaging actively in their academic chases (Men, Yue, & Liu, 2020).

School Climate and Resources

The overall school climate and availability of resources can impact academic adjustment. Supportive and inclusive school environments, well-appointed libraries, access to technology and academic support services contribute to students' ability to adjust academically (Cota, 2024).

Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic status can influence academic adjustment. Students from disadvantaged backgrounds may face additional challenges related to limited access to resources, lack of academic support and stressors outside of the academic dominion that can affect their adjustment and academic performance (Liu, Peng, & Luo, 2020).

Role of Academic Adjustment of University students

Academic adjustment theatres a vital role in the well-being and success of university students. Academic adjustment directly impacts students' academic performance. When students adjust well to the academic demands and prospects of the university, they are more likely to effectively engage with course material, participate in class discussions, complete assignments on time and perform well in exams. Academic adjustment sets the foundation for students to excel academically (Hazan Liran, & Miller, 2019).

Successful academic adjustment is closely linked to higher holding and graduation rates. When students feel comfortable and supported in their academic environment, they are more likely to persist and stay enrolled in their selected programs. On the other hand, poor academic adjustment may lead to academic release, disapproval and increased abrasion rates. Academic adjustment can significantly impact students' psychological well-being. A smooth transition into the university environment, along with effective adjustment to academic expectations, can reduce stress, anxiety and feelings of overwhelm. When students feel competent and successful academically, it contributes to their overall happiness, confidence and positive mental health (De Grift, Jansen, & Van Rooij, 2018).

Academic adjustment is closely tangled with social addition. When students adjust well academically, they often develop positive relationships with peers, faculty members, and support staff. These social connections and sense of belonging donate to a rich university experience, facilitating opportunities for teamwork, networking and personal growth. Academic adjustment fostering students' self-confidence and self-efficacy. As students navigate the challenges of higher education and achieve academic milestones, they develop a belief in their abilities, which can extend beyond academia. Positive academic adjustment empowers students to challenge future trials with flexibility and confidence (Roksa, & Kinsley, 2019). The contribution of family support to low-income students' academic success. Academic adjustment gives students the chance to acquire important skills for both their academic and professional careers. These skills include effective time management, organizational abilities, research, logical skills, written and oral communication, problem-solving and teamwork. By adjusting well academically, students acquire and improve these vital movable skills. Academic adjustment sets the stage for students' future career forecasts. A successful academic journey enhances students' qualifications, knowledge and competencies, increasing their employability. Employers often value candidates who have established strong academic adjustment as it reproduces their ability to adjust, learn and perform in professional settings (Wiek, Withycombe, & Redman, 2011).

Academic adjustment contributes to students' personal growth and development. It challenges students to enlarge their intellectual horizons, think critically, explore their passions and interests. By adjusting well academically, students engage in a transformative learning experience that broadens their perspectives and fosters lifelong learning. Academic adjustment influences students' level of engagement and motivation. When students feel connected to their academic environment, have supportive relationships with faculty members and observe their coursework as meaningful, they are more likely to be engaged and motivated to learn. Academic adjustment fuels students' interest, intrinsic motivation and desire to excel academically (Rahmatullah, Mulyasa, Syahrani, Pongpalilu, & Putri, 2022).

Academic adjustment sets the foundation for lifelong learning and engagement with the university community. Successful adjustment creates a positive affiliation with the university, leading to long-lasting connections with fellow alumni, faculty and staff. This network can provide ongoing support, mentorship, and opportunities for constant learning and professional development (Wyatt, 2011).

Relationship of Social & Academic Adjustment

Academic and social adjustment have a complex and profound interaction. The ability to successfully negotiate social interactions, build connections, and adapt to new social contexts is referred to as social adjustment. Conversely, academic adjustment denotes the capacity to adjust to the scholastic requirements, standards, and surroundings of learning environments. In order to transition socially and academically, social support is essential. Students frequently feel connected as a part of the academic community when they have good relationships with their instructors, peers, and other members. This social support can contribute to better academic adjustment by providing encouragement, motivation, and assistance in overcoming academic challenges. Equally, poor social adjustment such as feelings of social separation or lack of supportive relationships, can hinder academic adjustment by creating barriers to engagement, motivation and seeking help when needed (Shin, & Ryan, 2014).

Peer relationships can significantly impact academic adjustment. Positive peer relationships, characterized by friendship, collaboration and support, can improve academic adjustment by fostering a sense of going, facilitating learning through peer connections and providing social motivation. Students who feel socially related to their peers are more likely to engage in cooperative learning actions, seek help when needed, experience a positive academic environment. Conversely, difficulties in forming peer relationships or experiencing social conflicts can create stress, affect self-esteem, and hinder academic adjustment (Juvonen, Espinoza, & Knifsend, 2012).

The quality of student-teacher relationships can impact academic adjustment. Positive relationships with teachers, characterized by trust, support and effective communication, contribute to a supportive learning environment. Students who have helpful dealings with their instructors are more likely to be engaged, motivated and actively participate in their academic chases. Teacher support and guidance can provide valuable academic assistance, mentoring and encouragement, which positively impact academic adjustment. Conversely, strained or negative student-teacher relationships can impede academic adjustment by creating barriers to seeking help, reduced motivation, and a lack of support. Academic engagement, including active participation in class, interest in coursework, and a sense of academic purpose, can influence social adjustment. When students are academically promised, they are extra likely to interact with peers, collaborate on projects, and contribute to class discussions. Academic engagement facilitates social integration, as students connect with their peers through shared academic interests and experiences. Social adjustment benefits from increased opportunities for social interaction and the formation of social connections through academic engagement (Yunus, Osman, & Ishak, 2011).

Both social and academic adjustment contributes to self-confidence. Social adjustment, such as positive peer relationships and social acceptance, can enhance students' self-confidence in social states. Academic adjustment, including academic success, positive feedback from teachers and a sense of capability in their studies, also boosts self-confidence. In turn, self-confidence impacts both social and academic adjustment by promoting risk-taking, active participation and a positive mindset towards challenges. Social and academic adjustment are closely related to student well-being. Positive social adjustment, including supportive relationships and a sense of going, contributes to psychological happiness and can reduce stress and anxiety related to academic adjustment. Similarly, successful academic adjustment, including academic engagement and achievement, promotes a sense of achievement and satisfaction, positively influencing (Agbaria, 2020).

Research Objectives

1. To identify the social adjustment of the female students at university level.
2. To determine the academic adjustment of the female students at university level.
3. To find out the relationship between social adjustment and academic adjustment of the female students at university level.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of social adjustment of female students at university level?
2. What is the academic adjustment of female students at university level?
3. What is the relationship between social and academic adjustment of the female students at university level?

Research Methodology

The purpose of the current study was to examine the relationship between Social and Academic Adjustment of female university students in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The study was quantitative in nature and correlational research method was applied to conduct the research. A cross-sectional survey method was used for the data collection. The population of the study were consisted of all the BS level students of university of Kotli, AJ&K. the researcher selected 160 students using simple random sampling technique. The researcher used a self-formulated questionnaire for the collection of data. Five-point Likert scale used to get the responses of the respondents. The questionnaire was validated from three experts of the Department of Education, University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir. For the purpose of pilot testing, the questionnaire was distributed among 20 university students and they were not the part of the sample. The purpose of pilot testing was to check the readability and reliability of the instrument. The reliability of instrument was measured through Cronbach's alpha statistical technique with the help of SPSS software. The reliability of the instrument was 0.74 which was acceptable for conducting the final survey. The researcher personally visited the University of Kotli and collected the data from the respondents. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software 22 was used for the analysis of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage and mean for the analysis and interpretation of data. The results are presented in the form of tables.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive analysis of social adjustment of students at university

S. #	Statements	N	Mean
1.		160	2.05
2.	I adjust well to university	160	3.69
3.	I am pleased now about my choice to go to university	160	3.99
4.	I have several close social ties at university	160	2.26
5.	I am able to control my emotions very well	160	2.03
6.	I am satisfied to the level of my social participation	160	3.86
7.	I have been having a lot headache	160	3.78
8.	I have been having without regarding the value of university education	160	3.92
9.	I have been getting angry too easily	160	2.15
10.	I have good friends to talk about my problems	160	3.94
11.	I feel lonely a lot at university	160	3.76
12.	I feel I have good control over my life situation at university	160	3.08
13.	Since coming to this University, I have developed close personal relationship with other students	160	2.22
14.	Table 22. I am quite satisfied with my social life at university	160	2.04
15.	I feel I am very different from other students at university	160	4.03
16.	I can easily interact with others at university level	160	3.82

17.	I am meeting people and making friends	160	3.93
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The table presents the results of a survey conducted among university students, with numerical values indicating the level of agreement with various statements related to their university experience. On average, students reported moderate levels of adjustment to university life (3.69), high satisfaction with their choice to attend university (3.99), and satisfaction with their level of social participation (3.86). However, they reported having relatively few close social ties (2.26) and feeling somewhat lonely at university (3.76). Despite this, they reported relatively high levels of satisfaction with their social life (2.04) and the ability to make friends (3.93). Students reported moderate levels of control over their emotions (2.03), with some indicating they have been getting angry too easily (2.15), and experiencing headaches (3.78). Additionally, while many felt they could easily interact with others at the university level (3.82), some felt they were very different from other students (4.03), and fewer had developed close personal relationships with other students since coming to the university (2.22). Overall, the findings suggest a mixed experience among the students surveyed, with both positive and negative aspects of their university experience.

Table 2

Descriptive analysis of social adjustment of students at university

S. #	Statements	N	Mean
1.	I find academic work difficult at university	160	3.79
2.	I keep myself up to date on my abstract work	160	4.01
3.	I perform well during examinations	160	3.94
4.	I have been very efficient in the use of study time	160	3.49
5.	I am satisfied with the extracurricular activities at the University	160	2.53
6.	I am working as hard as I should at my course work	160	3.93
7.	I attend classes regularly	160	3.96
8.	I enjoy my academic work at university	160	3.94
9.	I am quite satisfied with my academics at university	160	3.93
10.	I am very satisfied with my teachers	160	3.89
11.	I am satisfied with my program of courses for this semester	160	3.86
12.	I have lot of trouble getting started on homework assignment	160	2,06
13.	I stay at this university for a bachelor’s degree	160	3.82

The table provides insights into the academic experiences of university students, with numerical values indicating the level of agreement with various statements related to their academic life. On average, students reported finding academic work moderately difficult (3.79) but keeping themselves up to date with their abstract work (4.01) and performing well during examinations (3.94). They indicated a high level of attendance in classes (3.96), satisfaction with their academic work (3.94), and satisfaction with their teachers (3.89). However, they reported some challenges with time management, with moderate efficiency in the use of study time (3.49) and occasional trouble getting started on homework assignments (2.06). While they expressed satisfaction with

their program of courses for the semester (3.86) and their intention to stay at the university for a bachelor's degree (3.82), they were less satisfied with extracurricular activities (2.53). Overall, the findings suggest that while students generally feel confident in their academic abilities and satisfied with their academic experiences, there are areas for improvement, particularly in time management and extracurricular activities.

Table 3

Analysis of Pearson Correlation between social and academic adjustment of university female students

	Mean	SD	R	P
Social Adjustment	3.79	0.623	.782	0.000
Academic Adjustment	3.92	0.599		

Table 3 shows the correlation between the social adjustment and academic adjustment of university female students. The mean and standard deviation of social adjustment were (M= 3.79, SD= 0.623) and emotional support (M= 3.92, SD= 0.599) and the significant value is $P= 0.000 < 0.05$. The value of correlation between them was $R= .782$ which show that it is a positive relation between the social adjustment and academic adjustment.

Discussion

The conclusion drawn from the study indicates that university students generally perform well academically and adjust well to university life. They are efficient in managing their study time and are diligent in their coursework. However, despite their academic success, students experience challenges related to social interaction, emotional control, and extracurricular engagement. Recent research supports these findings, emphasizing the importance of addressing students' social and emotional needs for overall well-being and academic success (El Ansari et al., 2020; Rogers et al., 2021). Studies have shown that positive social relationships and emotional well-being are closely linked to academic performance and overall satisfaction with university life (El Ansari et al., 2020). Therefore, universities should prioritize the development of supportive and inclusive environments that address students' social and emotional needs alongside their academic requirements.

The conclusion drawn from the study suggests that while university students generally attend classes regularly, enjoy their academic work, and are satisfied with their academics and teachers, they face challenges related to social integration and feelings of loneliness. Recent research supports these findings, emphasizing the significance of social relationships and emotional well-being for students' overall satisfaction and success in university settings (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2017; Muzaffar et al., 2021). Studies have shown that social connectedness and a sense of belonging are closely linked to students' well-being, academic performance, and retention (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2017; Muzaffar et al., 2021).

The conclusion drawn from the study also indicates a strong positive correlation between the social and academic adjustment of female university students. This suggests that the social life of students significantly influences their academic achievement and adjustment at the university level.

Recent research supports this conclusion, highlighting the importance of social integration and relationships for students' academic success and well-being (Soria & Stebleton, 2012; Ibrahim & Alkire, 2020). Studies have shown that students who feel socially connected and have a strong support network are more likely to perform well academically, adapt successfully to university life, and persist in their studies (Soria & Stebleton, 2012; Ibrahim & Alkire, 2020). Social integration not only provides students with emotional support but also facilitates academic engagement, motivation, and learning (Soria & Stebleton, 2012). Strong social ties and a sense of belonging contribute to students' overall satisfaction with university life, helping them navigate challenges and achieve their academic goals (Ibrahim & Alkire, 2020).

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that the students were good in academic work, adjust well in university and perform well during examination. They satisfied with the level of their social participation and they feel headache. Also the students have been very efficient in the use of study time, students worked hard as they should be in course work. On the other hand, students were feel nervous in front of their teachers and that they have several social ties at university and not able to control emotions very well. Students are also not satisfied with extracurricular activities at the university.
2. Students attended classes regularly, they have good friends to talk about their problems, they enjoy their academic work at university, they are satisfied with their academics, also satisfied with their teachers and they feel different from the other students at university. They are satisfied with the courses and students can easily interact with others at university level. While, the students feel alone and have good control over their life situation at university. They have not developed close relationship with other students and they are not satisfied with their social life of university and they have also face a lot of troubles for getting homework assignment from teachers.
3. It is concluded that there is strong positive correlation between the social and academic adjustment of university female students. It means that social life of the students affect the academic achievement/adjustment of students at university level.

Recommendations

1. Implement training programs for teachers to improve their communication and interpersonal skills, helping them create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment. Encourage teachers to provide regular feedback and guidance to students, helping to alleviate feelings of nervousness and improve academic performance. Establish open-door policies and regular office hours for teachers to address students' concerns and provide additional academic support as needed. Expand and enhance extracurricular activities and social events to promote stronger social ties and a sense of belonging among students.
2. Develop mentorship programs and peer support groups to help students build meaningful relationships and provide emotional support. Provide counseling services and workshops aimed at helping students develop better emotional regulation skills and cope with stress and anxiety effectively. Implement programs to help students achieve a better balance between their academic responsibilities and social life, emphasizing the importance of self-care and well-being.
3. Encourage students to participate in activities that promote both academic and personal growth, such as study groups, volunteer opportunities, and recreational activities. Provide

resources and guidance on time management and stress management techniques to help students manage their workload effectively and maintain a healthy work-life balance.

References

- Agbaria, Q. (2020). Predictors of personal and social adjustment among Israeli-Palestinian teenagers. *Child Indicators Research*, 13(3), 917-933.
- Alsaqqa, H. H. (2022). Building the culture of public health as a positive reflection from the COVID-19 crisis. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy*, 1683-1693.
- Bedi, A. (2021). No herd for black sheep: A meta-analytic review of the predictors and outcomes of workplace ostracism. *Applied Psychology*, 70(2), 861-904.
- Blake, M., & Gallimore, V. (2021). Understanding academics: a UX ethnographic research project at the University of York. In *Positioning the Academic Library within the University* (pp. 155-167). Routledge.
- Cogan, A., Pret, T., & Cardon, M. S. (2022). Everyday social support processes: Household members' instrumental and emotional support of entrepreneurs. *International Small Business Journal*, 40(5), 537-563.
- Cota, M. (2024). Relational & Collaborative: Librarian Leadership. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(2), 102848.
- Credé, M., & Niehorster, S. (2012). Adjustment to college as measured by the student adaptation to college questionnaire: A quantitative review of its structure and relationships with correlates and consequences. *Educational Psychology Review*, 24, 133-165.
- Decety, J. (2020). Empathy in medicine: what it is, and how much we really need it. *The American journal of medicine*, 133(5), 561-566.
- Domitrovich, C. E., Durlak, J. A., Staley, K. C., & Weissberg, R. P. (2017). Social-emotional competence: An essential factor for promoting positive adjustment and reducing risk in school children. *Child development*, 88(2), 408-416.
- Feeney, D. M. (2022). Positive self-talk: an emerging learning strategy for students with learning disabilities. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 57(3), 189-193.
- Garraway, J. (2021). Academics' learning in times of change: a change laboratory approach. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 43(2), 223-243.
- Gray, R., Vitak, J., Easton, E. W., & Ellison, N. B. (2013). Examining social adjustment to college in the age of social media: Factors influencing successful transitions and persistence. *Computers & Education*, 67, 193-207.
- Hazan Liran, B., & Miller, P. (2019). The role of psychological capital in academic adjustment among university students. *Journal of Happiness studies*, 20, 51-65
- Hu, S., Liu, H., Zhang, S., & Wang, G. (2020). Proactive personality and cross-cultural adjustment: Roles of social media usage and cultural intelligence. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 74, 42-57.
- Huang, L. (2020). Peer victimization, teacher unfairness, and adolescent life satisfaction: The mediating roles of sense of belonging to school and schoolwork-related anxiety. *School Mental Health*, 12(3), 556.
- Hudig, J., Scheepers, A. W., Schippers, M. C., & Smeets, G. (2023). Motivational mindsets, mindset churn and academic performance: The role of a goal-setting intervention and purpose in life. *Current Psychology*, 42(27), 23349-23368.
- Jones, S. M., & Bouffard, S. M. (2012). *Social and Emotional Learning in Schools: From Programs to Strategies*. Social Policy Report. Volume 26, Number 4. Society for Research in Child Development.

- Juvonen, J., Espinoza, G., & Knifsend, C. (2012). The role of peer relationships in student academic and extracurricular engagement. *Handbook of research on student engagement*, 387-401.
- Li, S., & Zizzi, S. (2018). A Case Study of International Students' Social Adjustment, Friendship Development, and Physical Activity. *Journal of International Students*, 8(1), 389-408.
- Liu, J., Peng, P., & Luo, L. (2020). The relation between family socioeconomic status and academic achievement in China: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32, 49-76.
- Maloney, D., Freeman, G., & Wohn, D. Y. (2020). " Talking without a Voice" Understanding Non-verbal Communication in Social Virtual Reality. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 4(CSCW2), 1-25.
- Maynard, C., Garcia, J., Lucietto, A., Hutzell, W., & Newell, B. (2021). Experiential Learning in the Energy Based Classroom. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*, 11(6)
- Maynard, C., Garcia, J., Lucietto, A., Hutzell, W., & Newell, B. (2021). Experiential Learning in the Energy Based Classroom. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*, 11(6).
- Men, L. R., Yue, C. A., & Liu, Y. (2020). "Vision, passion, and care:" The impact of charismatic executive leadership communication on employee trust and support for organizational change. *Public Relations Review*, 46(3), 101927.
- Monroe, M. C., Plate, R. R., Oxarart, A., Bowers, A., & Chaves, W. A. (2019). Identifying effective climate change education strategies: A systematic review of the research. *Environmental Education Research*, 25(6), 791-812.
- Naeem, M. (2020). Understanding the role of social media in organizational change implementation. *Management Research Review*, 43(9), 1097-1116.
- Nurdin, M. (2022). Regulation of the Education Rights of Persons with Disabilities in Law Number 8 of 2016 concerning Persons with Disabilities. *Legal Brief*, 11(2), 861-872.
- Patel, S. A., & Jansari, A. (2019). Social adjustment of student's in context with gender and habitat. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 7(4).
- Rahmatullah, A. S., Mulyasa, E., Syahrani, S., Pongpalilu, F., & Putri, R. E. (2022). Digital era 4.0: The contribution to education and student psychology. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 6(S3), 89-107.
- Raju, M. V. R., & Rahamtulla, T. K. (2007). Adjustment problems among school students. *Journal of the Indian academy of applied psychology*, 33(1), 73-79.
- Rienties, B., Beausaert, S., Grohnert, T., Niemantsverdriet, S., & Kommers, P. (2012). Understanding academic performance of international students: The role of ethnicity, academic and social integration. *Higher education*, 63, 685-700.
- Roksa, J., & Kinsley, P. (2019). The role of family support in facilitating academic success of low-income students. *Research in Higher Education*, 60, 415-436.
- Sadiki, H. (2020). Non-verbal Barriers to Cross-cultural Communication. *Journal of Research in Engineering, IT and Social Sciences*, 10(12), 25-34.
- Scanlan, J. N., Still, M., Radican, J., Henkel, D., Heffernan, T., Farrugia, P. & English, J. (2020). Workplace experiences of mental health consumer peer workers in New South Wales, Australia: A survey study exploring job satisfaction, burnout and turnover intention. *BMC psychiatry*, 20(1), 1-15.
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2021). Self-efficacy and human motivation. In *Advances in motivation science* (Vol. 8, pp. 153-179). Elsevier.

- Shin, H., & Ryan, A. M. (2014). Early adolescent friendships and academic adjustment: examining selection and influence processes with longitudinal social network analysis. *Developmental psychology*, 50(11), 2462.
- Simon, J. A. (2011). Legal issues in serving students with disabilities in postsecondary education. *New Directions for Student Services*, 2011(134), 95-107.
- Syakur, A., Zainuddin, H. M., & Hasan, M. A. (2020). Needs analysis English for specific purposes (esp) for vocational pharmacy students. *Budapest International Research and Critics in Linguistics and Education (BirLE) Journal*, 3(2), 724-733.
- Udvari-Solner, A., & Thousand, J. (2018). Effective organizational instructional and curricular practices in inclusive schools and classrooms. In *Towards inclusive schools?* (pp. 147-163). Routledge.
- Valente, S., Lourenço, A. A., & Németh, Z. (2020). School conflicts: Causes and management strategies in classroom relationships. *Interpersonal Relationships*. IntechOpen Limited.
- Vansteenkiste, M., Ryan, R. M., & Soenens, B. (2020). Basic psychological need theory: Advancements, critical themes, and future directions. *Motivation and emotion*, 44, 1-31.
- Voevoda, E. V. (2020). Intercultural communication in multicultural education space. *Training, Language and Culture*, 4(2), 11-20.
- Wang, M. T., & Sheikh-Khalil, S. (2014). Does parental involvement matter for student achievement and mental health in high school? *Child development*, 85(2), 610-625.
- Wiek, A., Withycombe, L., & Redman, C. L. (2011). Key competencies in sustainability: a reference framework for academic program development. *Sustainability science*, 6, 203-218.
- Wyatt, L. G. (2011). Nontraditional student engagement: Increasing adult student success and retention. *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 59(1), 10-20.
- Yunus, M. M., Osman, W. S. W., & Ishak, N. M. (2011). Teacher-student relationship factor affecting motivation and academic achievement in ESL classroom. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15, 2637-2641.
- Yurizka, Q., Simanjuntak, M. B., & Sihombing, J. (2022, May). SELF-ACCEPTANCE STUDY IN THE KOREAN DRAMA SERIES OUR BELOVED SUMMER (INTRINSIC ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN CHARACTER'S CHARACTER). In *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Inovasi Pendidikan*.
- El Ansari, W., Stock, C., & Mills, C. (2020). Is alcohol consumption associated with poor academic achievement in university students? *International Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 11, 22.
- Rogers, B., Sturges, D., & Miller, M. (2021). Addressing the mental health needs of college students. *Journal of College Student Psychotherapy*, 35(3), 176-191.
- Holt-Lunstad, J., Robles, T. F., & Sbarra, D. A. (2017). Advancing social connection as a public health priority in the United States. *American Psychologist*, 72(6), 517-530.
- Muzaffar, N., Hamid, S., & Anjum, A. (2021). Impact of social integration on academic stress among university students. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 36(1), 1-18.
- Ibrahim, N. K., & Alkire, R. W. (2020). The Influence of Social and Academic Integration on Student Retention in Higher Education. *Education Sciences*, 10(9), 221.
- Soria, K. M., & Stebleton, M. J. (2012). First-generation students' academic engagement and retention. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 17(6), 673-685.

